

Nitration and Halogenation Reactions of Salicylaldehydato Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II)

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Direct nitration and/or halogenation of salicylaldehydato complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) have been carried out. The substitution products have been characterised by elemental analyses, comparison with the authentic samples and with the help of ir spectra. The orientation of incoming substituents in the chelates is found to be same as in uncomplexed salicylaldehyde.

Prompted by our success in carrying out halogenation^{1,2}, nitration³⁻⁵, thiocyanation⁶, acetylation⁷ and formylation⁷ reactions on metal 1,3-diketones during the last few years, we have carried out a few similar substitution reactions on the salicylaldehydato complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with a view to examining the stability of these chelates under the substitution reaction conditions as well as the orienting influence of the chelate for incoming substituents.

3,5,3',5'-Tetranitrosalicylaldehydato Cu(II) (II, R = NO₂, M = Cu) and 3,5,3',5'-tetrabromosalicylaldehydato Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) (II, R = Br, M = Cu, Co, Ni) have been prepared by direct substitution of nitro and bromo groups into the appropriate unsubstituted chelate I for the first time. These derivatives were characterised by comparison

with the authentic samples obtained by complexing 3,5-dinitrosalicylaldehyde or 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde with the respective metal ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bis(salicylaldehydato)-Co(II) and *-Cu(II)* were prepared following the procedure reported by Tyson and Adams⁸ but *bis(salicylaldehydato)-Ni(II)* could not be prepared by that procedure. It was, however, prepared by treating a saturated solution of nickel

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nitrate in ethanol with stoichiometric amount of salicylaldehyde and then adding a saturated solution of sodium carbonate with constant stirring until the effervescence ceased. The precipitated product was filtered, washed first with aqueous ethanol, then with ether and finally dried under vacuum.

Bis-(3,5-dinitrosalicylaldehydato)-Cu(II) i.e. (II, $M = Cu$, $R = NO_2$): Bis-(salicylaldehydato)-Cu(II) (0.5 g., 0.0016 mole) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) were taken in a 250 ml. Erlenmeyer flask fitted with a calcium chloride drying tube and stirred magnetically over an ice-bath for 15 min. Powdered $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ (0.80 g, 0.0032 mole) was added in small portions over a period of 30 min. and the ice-bath removed after 2 hr. but the stirring was continued for additional 4 hr. Undue rise in temperature because of the exothermic reaction was checked by occasionally dipping the flask in ice-cold water. The resulting green coloured slurry was decomposed by pouring into 100 ml. of ice-cold water containing sufficient amount of sodium acetate and stirring for an hour. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered under suction, washed first with water, then with ethanol and twice recrystallized from hot ethanol. Yield of the yellow crystalline tetranitro complex containing a molecule of ethanol was 0.28 g, m.p. 339–41°. (Found : C, 35.56; H, 2.1; N, 11.1; $C_{14}H_6N_4O_{12}Cu \cdot C_2H_5OH$ requires : C, 36.1; H, 2.3; N, 10.5%).

3,5-Dinitrosalicylaldehyde (III, $R = NO_2$) prepared described in the literature⁹ was converted into bis-(3,5-dinitrosalicylaldehydato)-Cu(II) by the method of Houghton and Pointer¹⁰. This product was found to be identical to the tetranitro complex obtained by the direct nitration of bis-(salicylaldehydato)-Cu(II).

Bromination of bis-(salicylaldehydato)-Cu(II) with bromine in acetic acid was unsuccessful and the product probably arising out of decomposition of the original complex could not be identified.

Bis-(3,5-dibromosalicylaldehydato)-Cu(II) i.e. (II, $M = Cu$, $R = Br$): To a 20 ml. solution of bis-(salicylaldehydato)-Cu II (0.5 g., 0.0016 mole) in dimethylformamide, a stoichiometric amount of N-bromosuccinimide contained in 15 ml. DMF solvent was added. After stirring the mixture for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. at room temperature, it was poured into a beaker containing 300 ml. of cold distilled water. The resulting yellow coloured precipitate was filtered, washed with water, redissolved in DMF, filtered and finally reprecipitated from the filtrate by adding water. The solid obtained on filtration was successively washed with water, ethanol and ether and dried under vacuum. Yield, 0.43 g., m.p. 330–32°. (Found : C, 27.19; H, 1.2; $C_{14}H_6O_4Br_4Cu$ requires : C, 27.04; H, 0.96%).

Identity of the product was confirmed by comparison with a sample of II ($M = Cu$, $R = Br$) obtained directly from 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde¹¹ (III, $R = Br$) ligand.

Bis-(3,5-dibromosalicylaldehydato)-Co(II) i.e. (II, $M = Co$, $R = Br$): This derivative was prepared from bis-(salicylaldehydato)-Co(II) and N-bromosuccinimide by a similar procedure as described above for the tetrabromo copper chelate. A pale yellow crystalline product was obtained in nearly quantitative yield, m.p. 314–16°. (Found : C, 26.95; H, 1.30; $C_{14}H_6O_4Br_4Co$ requires : C, 27.22; H, 0.97%). It was found to be identical to the product obtained directly from 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde (III, $R = Br$) and cobalt acetate.

Bis-(3,5-dibromosalicylaldehydato)-Ni(II) i.e. (II, $M = Ni$, $R = Br$): By following a bromination procedure similar to that described above, bis-(salicylaldehydato)-Ni(II) and N-bromosuccinimide yielded the title compound as light greenish crystalline solid in almost quantitative yield, m.p. 243–45°. (Found: C, 27.13; H, 1.20; $C_{14}H_6O_4Br_4Ni$ requires: C, 27.20; H, 0.97%). This product was comparable to that obtained directly from 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde (III, $R = Br$) and nickel acetate.

Attempted iodination of bis-(salicylaldehydato)-Cu(II) with iodine monochloride in DMF solvent resulted in the isolation of only 3,5-diiodosalicylaldehyde¹². The same product was also isolated when iodine monochloride was reacted with bis-(salicylaldehydato)-Co(II).

Attempted chlorination of (I, $M = Cu$) and (I, $M = Co$) with N-chlorosuccinimide in DMF solution gave unexpected products which could not be identified.

The i.r. spectra used for the study of structures were recorded in the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer Model 521 infrared spectrophotometer with KBr discs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As the salicylaldehydato complexes under study are unstable in presence of nitric acid, a mild nitrating agent-acetyl nitrate, prepared *in situ* was employed. Nitronium ions produced from this reagent act as electrophile to form the resonance stabilized σ -complex intermediates (IVa, b) as follows:

Removal of a proton from each of these intermediates and further reaction of each of the dinitro chelates with the NO_2^+ ion in the same manner yields (II, $\text{M} = \text{Cu}$, $\text{R} = \text{NO}_2$). However, positions 4 and 6 in the benzene ring are not attacked by the electrophile as that would tend to place a positive charge at a carbon adjacent to an atom already carrying a positive charge in the σ -complex intermediate creating an energetically unfavourable situation.

Although iodine monochloride successfully iodinate metal, 1,3-diketone chelates¹, the same reagent treated with (I, $\text{R} = \text{Cu}$) or (I, $\text{R} = \text{Co}$) yielded only 3,5-diiodosalicylaldehyde. It is likely that iodine monochloride iodinate the benzene ring in the chelate, producing hydrogen chloride in sufficient concentration which acts to destroy the chelate ring.

The orientation of incoming substituents in the chelates is found to be the same as for the uncomplexed salicylaldehyde.

The infrared spectral bands for $\nu(\text{C} = \text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ of seven complexes derived from salicylaldehyde and its derivatives are recorded in Table I. Broadly, it appears that the

TABLE I

Carbonyl and Metal-Oxygen Str. frequencies (cm^{-1}) in some metal salicylaldehydato complexes and their derivatives

	Compound	$\nu(\text{C} = \text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$
I,	$\text{M} = \text{Cu}$	1610s	615m
II,	$\text{M} = \text{Cu}; \text{R} = \text{NO}_2$	1630s	595m
II,	$\text{M} = \text{Cu}; \text{R} = \text{Br}$	1625s	575m
I,	$\text{M} = \text{Co}$	1660s	585m
II,	$\text{M} = \text{Co}; \text{R} = \text{Br}$	1655s	560m
I,	$\text{M} = \text{Ni}$	1650s	590m
II,	$\text{M} = \text{Ni}; \text{R} = \text{Br}$	1655s	575m

s = strong, m = medium.

strength of the $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bond in the chelate depends on the extent to which the $\text{C} = \text{O}$ bond of the ligand has been weakened. This seems to be obvious, if the electrons of the benzene ring do not have any resonance interaction with those of the chelate ring.

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